

Annex 3: Communication and Data Management Guidelines for WGs

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“Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research, and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research.”
(ARRA, 10th commitment)

“Ensure independence and transparency of the data, infrastructure and criteria necessary for research assessment and for determining research impacts; in particular by clear and transparent data collection, algorithms and indicators, by ensuring control and ownership by the research community over critical infrastructures and tools, and by allowing those assessed to have access to the data, analyses and criteria used.” (Overarching principle from the ARRA)

1. Purpose of this document

The CoARA Research Data Management Guidelines brings together good documentation and data management practices, relevant support from the CoARA Secretariat as well as the publication policy of Working Groups' outputs. The overall aim of the guidelines is 1.) to establish shared process- and output-related practices across the CoARA WGs that help maximise the quality and impact of their outputs, 2.) to enable the coalition at large to easily develop an overview of and connect to these outputs and eventually 3.) to facilitate their implementation across, and possibly beyond, CoARA. The document is a response to a request made by WG Chairs during the first CoARA WG (Co-)Chairs Forum in November 2023.

The WGs' endorsement framework is to be built on top of these guidelines in the second half of 2024.

Please note that the document herein is a living document that follows the evolution of CoARA. Communities around CoARA, and especially contributors to CoARA Working Groups are invited to provide constructive feedback on its usefulness and to suggest amendments. Please contact us with your feedback at secretariat@coara.eu with the email subject: 'Feedback on RDM guidelines for Working Groups'.

The guidelines are preceded by section 2 on communication in order to inform the guidelines and to centralise information for WGs

2. CoARA Working Groups and communication

All CoARA Working Group (Co-)Chairs and WP4 partners and have been added to the dedicated SharePoint "[CoARA_WG_Co-Chairs_Support](#)". If there are any changes within your Working Groups and you need to add or remove specific members from the SharePoint and associated distribution list (CoARA_WG_Co-Chairs_Support@esf.org), please inform us by contacting the CoARA Secretariat at secretariat@coara.eu.

If you need to request changes to the information about your WG already available on the CoARA website or to request the inclusion of additional information about possible events, online surveys, etc. of your WG, kindly use the dedicated [online form](#).

There is an ongoing effort to enrich the current WG pages of the CoARA website and the CoARA Secretariat team will gladly collaborate with you to tailor the appearance of your webpage to your specification.

2.1 Collaboration among WGs

2.1.1 SharePoint workspace

For internal communication, the CoARA Secretariat set up a SharePoint environment for WGs (Co-)Chairs as a workspace for sharing documentation and keeping track of the activities performed. Once a new contact needs to be given access to it, the Secretariat is to be notified through the secretariat@coara.eu email address.

Name	Modified	Modified By
Early-and-mid-Career Researchers (EMCRs) ...	November 27, 2023	Sofia SEHIN
Ethics and Research Integrity Policy in Resp...	17 minutes ago	Sofia SEHIN
Experiments in Assessment – Idea generati...	November 27, 2023	Sofia SEHIN
General	November 24, 2023	Sofia SEHIN
Global framework for research evaluation in...	16 minutes ago	Sofia SEHIN
Improving practices in the assessment of re...	November 27, 2023	Sofia SEHIN
Multilingualism and language biases in rese...	November 27, 2023	Sofia SEHIN
Recognizing and Rewarding Peer Review	November 27, 2023	Sofia SEHIN
Reforming Academic Career Assessment	November 27, 2023	Sofia SEHIN
Responsible metrics and indicators	November 27, 2023	Sofia SEHIN
Supporting the alignment of research asses...	November 27, 2023	Sofia SEHIN
TIER - Towards an Inclusive Evaluation of Re...	16 minutes ago	Sofia SEHIN
Towards Open Infrastructures for Responsib...	November 24, 2023	Sofia SEHIN
Towards Transformations Transdisciplinarity,...	November 27, 2023	Sofia SEHIN

Fig. 1. Directory of the WG (Co-)Chairs SharePoint workspace

As Fig. 1. shows, the directory consists of folders for each WG as well as a 'General' folder. Each WG (Co-)Chairs (and possibly other support roles to WGs) have access to each folder. In the WG's folders WGs can share progress and internal resources with each other, for instance, updated work plans, planned deliverables and other materials as well as surveys or draft outputs for internal feedback among the (Co-)Chairs. The 'Generic' folder contains all the support material that is equally relevant to all (Co-)Chairs, such as the CoARA communications toolkit (see Fig.2.).

Fig. 2. 'Generic' folder at the WG (Co-)Chairs SharePoint with resources

Users of this SharePoint workspace are invited to populate it as it works best for their needs.

2.1.2 Mailing list

In addition to the shared workspace, Working Group (Co-)Chairs also have a dedicated mailing list: CoARA_WG_Co-Chairs_Support@esf.org, which can be used both as a discussion forum among (Co-)Chairs or to inform them about any CoARA update. A dedicated [Teams channel](#) has also been set up to streamline communication processes.

Fig. 3. CoARA WG (Co-)Chairs Teams channel and mailing list

2.1.3. Collecting and managing personal data

The CoARA Secretariat and the CoARA Boost project collect the following information from WGs: contact information to WG (Co-)Chairs, WG outputs and progress reports, workplans, administration data of the WGs travel support envelopes (3000 EUR per year), data associated with their dissemination and outreach activities, including event recordings and registration data associated with them. These data collection processes strictly adhere to the GDPR regulation¹⁴. In this document there is a managed access procedure in place for authorized users of personal data. The contact details of the Data Protection Officer (DPO) will be available to all data subjects involved in the WGs support related activities. Technical measures are implemented to control systems such as devices, networks and hardware, which includes:

- Firewall, anti-virus protection and updates of software that required to perform project's tasks,
- Pseudonymization and anonymization,

¹⁴ The implementation of GDPR regulations are safeguarded by the CoARA Secretariat host institution, ESF's Privacy Policy. Available at <https://www.esf.org/privacy-policy/>.

- Restricted access to the files and folders with personal data, protected by passwords changed in a timely manner.

All the partners involved in personal data processing will include organizational measures in place, as such:

- Security policy,
- Due diligence to check the processor before their commitment if they are compliant with GDPR.

2.1.4. Internal Communications within CoARA: Coalition Members Newsletter

The members' newsletter is published quarterly and is a vector to distribute progress made and activities to the broader CoARA membership¹⁵. WGs are strongly encouraged to contribute to the newsletter. The Secretariat will reach out to all (Co-) Chairs (see 2.1.2.) prior to circulation to enquire about contributions. (Co-) Chairs can, however, reach out to the Secretariat anytime to proactively share content considered suitable for circulation (email: communication@coara.eu). Any individual of a CoARA member organisation is eligible to sign up to the CoARA members newsletter, this can be done via the following link: <https://coara.eu/sign-up-for-the-coara-members-newsletter/>.

2.2 Use of the CoARA logo and funding statement

Forming a distinguished pillar of CoARA, WGs are welcome to use the CoARA logo for their activities and outputs. This can be downloaded from the 'Communication toolkit' folder of the SharePoint workspace. In addition, Working Groups are also encouraged to design their own logos for which they can build on the CoARA logo. To ensure coherency with CoARA's visual identity, WGs are kindly requested to keep the Secretariat informed on the aforementioned related activities and asked to reach out for requesting feedback on, or support to, their WGs' logo productions: communication@coara.eu. Information and guidance on CoARA's visual identity can also be found within the Communication toolkit available within the Working Group workspace (detailed in 1.1.1.).

¹⁵ <https://coara.eu/coalition/membership/>

Fig. 4. CoARA logo with subheading.

Fig. 5. Simple CoARA logo without subheading.

WGs are encouraged to use the CoARA logo (Fig. 4. and Fig. 5.). In case of however in doubt, WGs are encouraged to reach out to the CoARA Secretariat.

All beneficiaries, managing authorities and implementing partners of EU funding must use the EU emblem in their communication to acknowledge the support received under EU programmes. It must be displayed prominently and correctly, in combination with a simple funding statement that mentions the EU's support. Logo can be downloaded here: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information-sources/logo-download-center_en¹⁶

¹⁶ The funding acknowledgement logo is available in multiple languages: 24 EU language and 14 non-EU languages

Fig. 6. EU Funding logos

The emblem is preferably reproduced on a white background. Avoid a background of varied colours, and in any case, one that does not go with blue. If there is no alternative to a coloured background, put a white border around the rectangle, with the width of this being equal to twenty-fifth of the height of the rectangle.

The following disclaimer should be included next to the EU emblem:

“Views and opinions expressed are, however, of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the REA can be held responsible for them.”

2.3 External communication

Zenodo (see 2.1.) is the repository chosen for uploading files¹⁷ and publishing them openly. Working Groups are expected to facilitate this process autonomously.

Webpages will be created for each Working Group, linked to the CoARA website, and curated by the Secretariat. Content from Zenodo can be linked to the CoARA website or the WG’s webpage upon request. The webpages will include the WG’s mission, work plan, and membership. Events and activities (such as surveys) can also be linked to the webpage. Communities, such as LinkedIn communities and Slack channels, can also be linked to the webpage. A contact point for each WG will be listed on the website, after consenting to its publication. An overview of all Working Groups can be found here: <https://coara.eu/coalition/working-groups/>. The Secretariat will reach out to the WGs to inform them once the pages are set up. The WGs are kindly requested to collaborate on the webpages and provide content, as well as inform the Secretariat of any updates or changes: please email secretariat@coara.eu and in Cc communication@coara.eu.

¹⁷ White papers, analyses, presentations, reports, etc.

Working Groups are expected to disseminate their activities, events and outputs and involving the CoARA communication channels (news items, later possibly guest blog posts on the website, [X](#), [Mastodon](#), [LinkedIn](#), [YouTube](#) channels). For that, they should flag early upcoming activities and events so this can be planned by the Secretariat, and send the materials to be disseminated to communication@coara.eu at their earliest convenience. By default, these will be processed and published within a week, however subject to the request (e.g., support in cutting and editing a video requires more time and resources than linking an uploaded Zenodo file to the CoARA website).

In addition, the membership of a CoARA Working Group is expected to leverage their own networks and raise awareness of the Working Group's activities. For social media activity, it is advised to work with the CoARA hashtag: #ReformingRA and link to CoARA using the handles¹⁸.

In general, it would be appreciated if the membership of a Working Group could support CoARA by raising awareness of CoARA activities, following CoARA's social media platforms, and sharing news. CoARA circulates milestone news and campaigns with communication professionals, Working Group members are asked to sign up their communication department or professional to the distribution list: <https://coara.eu/coara-communication-media-professionals-distribution-list/>

3. Publication policy for the Working Group outputs

CoARA follows the principle of making publications openly accessible. Zenodo is the primary repository to make content and innovations publicly available and to be linked back to the CoARA website.

3.1. Publication of the outputs on Zenodo

WGs' outputs can be manyfold, including guidelines and recommendations, collections of good practices, reports from pilots, white papers, reports from workshops or conferences, toolkits, games and interactive tools. As the Rules of Procedure for Working Groups¹⁹ document specifies under the headings 2.6. and 2.7., WGs should by default openly disseminate the results from their work. Some WGs may however not share some

¹⁸ X (Twitter): @CoARAssessment

LinkedIn: Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment

Mastodon: @CoARAssessment

YouTube: @CoARAssessment

¹⁹ CoARA Rules of Procedure - Working Groups. Version 1.0. Published 20 Oct. 2022.

https://coara.eu/app/uploads/2022/10/CoARA_RoPs_Working_Groups_v1.0.pdf Last accessed 20/02/2024.

results, when such results have a confidential nature or when the WG is meant to share information that is particularly sensitive to members. The decision of not sharing results shall be taken by the WG members and a motivation should be provided to the Steering Board for its approval.

Following the decision to publish the results, where possible, (Co-)Chairs should make their outputs available as part of the CoARA Working Groups Zenodo collection (<https://coara.eu/coalition/working-groups/>). See Zenodo Guidelines for CoARA (in the next section) for more details. WGs are welcome to publish also other documents, such as their presentations in the collection. The collection is curated by the CoARA Secretariat.

3.1.1 Zenodo guidelines for CoARA WGs

Step 1: Accessing Zenodo

Go to the Zenodo website: <https://zenodo.org/>

Sign in to your Zenodo account using your credentials. If you do not have an account, you can create one by following the registration process.

Step 2: Uploading Your Action Plan File

To start, select a community where you want to submit your record. Select the CoARA Working Groups community. Importantly, you can flexibly link one record to multiple communities (such as your institution's community), even after its publication.

Fig. 7: Zenodo community

From your Zenodo dashboard, click on the "Upload" button. Choose "Publication" from the content types.

1. Select the file from your computer that you wish to upload. Ensure that your file is in an appropriate format (e.g., PDF, Word document).

Fig. 8: Uploading files to Zenodo

2. Fill in the required metadata, including title, authors, description, and keywords. Please ensure that you mention "CoARA" in the keywords for easy identification.

3. Digital Object Identifier (DOI): If you do not have a DOI, you can automatically create one by choosing the 'No' option and then selecting the 'Get a DOI now' button.

Fig. 9: Creating an DOI for Zenodo

If you have a DOI that you would like to associate with this submission, enter it in the provided field.

Basic information

III Digital Object Identifier*

Do you already have a DOI for this upload? Yes No

Copy/paste your existing DOI here...

A DOI allows your upload to be easily and unambiguously cited. Example: 10.1234/foo.bar

Fig. 10: Associating a DOI to Zenodo

4. Under 'Communities' select **'CoARA Working Groups'** to associate your upload with our community.

zenodo Search records... Communities My dashboard

Select the community where you want to submit your record. Select a community

Select a community

All My communities CoARA

CoARA Working Groups [↗](#)
This collection brings together outputs of CoAR...
Topic Owner Select

CoARA National Chapters Exchange Forum 2024 [↗](#)
Representatives of CoARA's 15 National Chapters...
Event Owner Select

« < 1 2 > »

Close

Fig. 11: Select the 'CoARA Working Groups' Zenodo Community

5. Review the licensing options and select the one that aligns with your preferences for sharing and reuse.

6. Click Save and Publish to submit your document.

The screenshot shows a 'Draft' status at the top. Below it are two buttons: 'Save draft' and 'Preview'. A large green 'Publish' button is prominently displayed. Underneath is a 'Visibility' section with a shield icon and a red asterisk. It shows 'Files only' with 'Public' selected over 'Restricted'. A green box with an open lock icon and the text 'Public' states 'The record and files are publicly accessible.' At the bottom, there is an 'Options' section with a checkbox for 'Apply an embargo' and a help icon, with a note that 'Record or files protection must be restricted to apply an embargo.'

Fig. 12: Submit documents to Zenodo

Step 3: Notify CoARA Secretariat

Please send an email to secretariat@coara.eu once you have uploaded your document. Include the title and DOI of your upload for easy reference.

Note:

If you have multiple versions of the document, we kindly ask you to create a new version on Zenodo rather than uploading separate files.

Thank you for your valuable contribution to CoARA's research assessment initiatives. Your participation is instrumental in advancing our collective goals

3.2 Licensing

To enable easy interaction with and reusability of WGs outputs and to remain consistent with the guiding principles of the ARRA, a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) should be used for them by default, unless the content of the output (e.g. in case it contains sensitive data) makes it impossible. Intellectual property rights always stay with the creators. Licensing information should be clearly indicated in the metadata

as well as on the outputs, in the case of the latter by using the symbol. This collection and the records belonging to each WG will also be linked back to the CoARA website.

3.3. Versioning

Outputs can be added to the Zenodo collection both prior to or after possible endorsement or community review processes around them. The versioning possibilities of the Zenodo infrastructure can easily enable keeping track of the evolution of these outputs.

5. Data Management Guidelines

Open and FAIR data management practices are paving the way for high-quality and transparent research (and research-related) processes and outputs. To enable members of the WGs as well as the broadest CoARA community to safely rely on WGs outputs and maximise their (re)use potential, the CoARA Secretariat recommends considering the high-level principles below for WGs processes and outputs.

5.1. Rich documentation

Investing in the documentation of data collection and research processes and making decisions made, standards selected etc. explicit do not only form a cornerstone aspect of successful collaboration and teamwork, but it also leads to robustness, openness, transparency of results and outputs. As a result, they can be viewed, managed, accessed and ultimately assessed in terms of the integrity of processes, rather than only as products.

5.2. Use of open infrastructure, tools, formats and licenses where possible

In line with the overarching openness principle of the ARRA, WGs shall strive for basing their work on open infrastructure, tools, formats and licenses where possible to ensure transparency of their resources and their independence from proprietary black-box infrastructure. This enables control and ownership by the research community over these resources and significantly enhances their reusability as open data, tools, or publications.

5.3. Generous citation practices

Giving credit to all contributors and reflecting this in the ownership of resources is a central principle of the ARRA. Similarly to showcasing collaborative effort, citing all content types (services, tools, code, corpora) used or having relevance to the processes and the outputs also facilitates the transparency and reusability of results and enhances their citation culture – a necessary precondition of gaining recognition for these born-digital content

types. WGs are encouraged to recommend data citation formats (cite as...) for their resources.

5.4. Use of Persistent Identifiers

Where possible, Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) shall be used for authors, institutions, funding programmes and types of resources (data, papers etc). This ensures that locations of and key information about these resources remain stable and easily identifiable both for humans and machines. Interlinking these PIDs is a leap towards a more holistic data economy for research assessment.